

Structure-dependent QED corrections to $\rho \rightarrow \pi\pi$ decays and their impact on the HVP contribution to the muon $g-2$

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Abstract

Isospin breaking (IB) in the rho meson parameters is an important input to correct the $\tau \rightarrow \pi\pi\nu_\tau$ spectral function that is used to predict the dominant hadronic vacuum polarization (HVP) contribution to the muon $g-2$. We summarize our recent results on the computation of the $\rho \rightarrow \pi\pi(\gamma)$ width difference and final-state photon radiation (FSR) corrections in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-(\gamma)$ including the electromagnetic structure of hadrons. The impact of both sources of IB in the muon $g-2$ is assessed.

1 Introduction

In the data-driven prediction of the muon $g-2$ anomaly, the dominant contribution to HVP is provided by the measured $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ bare cross section data below $\sqrt{s} = 2$ GeV (s is the invariant mass of two pions). The *bare* normalized mass distribution of two pions $(N_{\pi\pi^0})^{-1}dN_{\pi\pi^0}/ds$ produced in $\tau^\pm \rightarrow \pi^\pm\pi^0\nu_\tau$ decays can also be used to predict this HVP, after the measured distribution is: 1) undressed from long-distance electromagnetic $G_{EM}(s)$ and electroweak short-distance S_{EW} radiative corrections, 2) added final-state radiation $FSR(s)$ effects in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$, 3) corrected for appropriate phase-space factors $\beta_0^3(s)/\beta_+^3(s)$, where $\beta_0(s)$ ($\beta_+(s)$) is the pion velocity in the rest frame of the di-pion system and, 4) multiplied by the factor $|F_V(s)/f_+(s)|^2$, the ratio of electromagnetic $F_V(s)$ and weak $f_+(s)$ pion form factors. All these corrections are collectively called isospin-breaking (IB) corrections, such that the HVP prediction for the muon anomaly based on tau data becomes [1]:

$$a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi] = \frac{\alpha^2 m_\tau^2}{6|V_{ud}|^2 \pi^2} \frac{\mathcal{B}_{\pi\pi^0}}{\mathcal{B}_e} \int_{4m_\pi^2}^{m_\tau^2} ds \frac{K(s)}{s} \frac{1}{N_{\pi\pi^0}} \frac{dN_{\pi\pi^0}}{ds} \left[(1 - \hat{s})^2 (1 + 2\hat{s}) \right]^{-1} \left[\frac{R_{\text{IB}}(s)}{S_{\text{EW}}} \right], \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{s} \equiv s/m_\tau^2$, \mathcal{B}_X is the branching ratio of tau decay into channel X and $K(s)$ the QED kernel. The energy-dependent IB corrections are grouped in the factor

$$R_{\text{IB}}(s) = \frac{FSR(s)}{G_{EM}(s)} \left(\frac{\beta_0(s)}{\beta_+(s)} \right)^3 \left| \frac{F_V(s)}{f_+(s)} \right|^2. \quad (2)$$

The status of these IB corrections and current uncertainties in the HVP muon $g-2$ are summarized in the 2025 White Paper (WP25) of the Theory Initiative [1].

The IB effects are quantified by $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi]$, the difference between Eq. (1) and the result without considering these effects ($R_{\text{IB}}(s) = S_{\text{EW}} = 1$). Previous studies of this quantity, using different models for the form factors of the pion in (2), obtain consistent results with similar uncertainties (in units 10^{-10} , throughout this paper), namely: $-14.9(1.9)$ [2, 3] and

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$-15.2^{(+2.3)}_{(-2.6)}$ [4]. The recommended value in WP25 [1] is $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi] = -15.0(5.0)$, with a larger uncertainty associated with a possible large IB in the $\rho\pi\pi$ coupling involved in the calculation of the $\rho^\pm - \rho^0$ width difference.

So far, the $O(\alpha)$ electromagnetic corrections giving rise to $G_{\text{EM}}(s)$, FSR(s) and part of the width difference of ρ mesons, have been computed without considering the electromagnetic structure of hadrons (also called scalar QED approximation or sQED). While the width difference of ρ mesons can be extracted from experiment, its value is usually model- and process-dependent [5]. In addition, the accuracy of present data is not sufficient to reduce the uncertainty assigned in the WP25. An alternative approach [2–4] makes use of the theoretical prediction of the width difference, which was first calculated in Ref. [6] using sQED (owing to this approximation, a 10% error was assigned to the $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi]$, as well as to the contribution stemming from the FSR correction [2, 4]). Here, we summarize our recent results of the calculation of this width difference by incorporating the electromagnetic structure of the hadrons involved and the $\rho\pi\pi\gamma$ vertex [7]. Our calculation of the radiative corrections to $\rho^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ decays, allows us to describe also the structure-dependent effects in the FSR(s) corrections as described below.

2 $\rho^\pm - \rho^0$ width difference

Rho vector mesons predominantly decay into $\pi\pi$ and $\pi\pi\gamma$ (their sum is denoted as $\pi\pi(\gamma)$). Decays into other (‘rest’) channels have individual small branching fractions ($\leq 10^{-4}$) [5]. Therefore, the difference of total widths can be written as [7]

$$\Delta\Gamma_\rho \equiv \Gamma_{\rho^0} - \Gamma_{\rho^\pm} = \Delta\Gamma_\rho[\pi\pi(\gamma)] + \Delta\Gamma_\rho[\text{rest}], \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta\Gamma_\rho[\text{rest}] = +0.085(17)$ MeV from measured values [5]. The first term in Eq. (3) receives IB contributions from the pion-mass difference (-1.04 MeV), the rho-mass difference $\Delta m_\rho = m_{\rho^\pm} - m_{\rho^0}$ ($-217\Delta m_\rho/m_\rho$ MeV) and from the difference of radiative corrections ($\delta_0 - \delta_+$) to $\rho \rightarrow \pi\pi$ decays, including real photons of all allowed energies [6, 7].

The radiative corrections to $\rho \rightarrow \pi\pi$ decays were first computed in [6], using the sQED approximation. In addition, a truncated version of the $\rho\rho\gamma$ vertex (convection approximation) was used [6] in order to keep finite the corrections involving the electromagnetic vertex of the charged rho meson. Recently, in Ref. [7] we have extended our previous calculation by incorporating the electromagnetic structure of pions and rho mesons and including the full $\rho\rho\gamma$ vertex.

In Ref. [7], structure-dependent effects were introduced by attaching a factor $F(k^2) = \sum_V a_V M_V^2 / (M_V^2 - k^2)$ to the point-pion electromagnetic vertex in virtual corrections ($M_V^2 \equiv m_V^2 - im_V\Gamma_V$, with $V = \rho, \rho', \rho''$, and m_V, Γ_V the mass and width of V mesons, taken as adjustable parameters fitted from experimental data [8]). Due to G-parity, we have assumed [7] that the isovector meson resonances can be used to mediate the ρ^\pm electromagnetic vertex with the same form factor $F(k^2)$. This is of course an assumption given the absence of good experimental data in the resonances region; although this model can be motivated by vector dominance, the coefficients a_V are not necessarily the same.

The calculation of the radiative corrections to $\rho \rightarrow \pi\pi$, with inclusive photons, leads to the values [7] (taken at the mass scale $m_\rho = 775$ MeV)

$$\delta_0 = 6.04(2) \times 10^{-3}, \quad \text{and} \quad \delta_+ = 2.10(5) \times 10^{-3}. \quad (4)$$

The radiative corrections are defined as $\Gamma[\rho^i \rightarrow \pi\pi(\gamma)] = \Gamma^0(\rho^i \rightarrow \pi\pi)[1 + \delta_i]$, with $i = +, 0$ and the superscript 0 denotes the tree-level rate. The new values of radiative corrections yields an IB in the rho width difference of $+0.591(8)$ MeV, compared to $+1.8(2)$ MeV of our previous calculation [6] used as input in Refs. [2, 4]. This difference is due, not only to the structure-dependent effects, but also to the use of the complete ρ electromagnetic vertex in our new calculation [7].

Figure 1: Radiative corrections to the $\rho^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ including electromagnetic structure (blue solid-line [7]) compared to the sQED approximation of Ref. [6] (dotted-line) the Schwinger's result [9] (red dashed-line). Final state corrections are corresponds to $\text{FSR}(s) = 1 + \delta_0(s)$.

Taking into account the mass difference of pions and the width difference arising from subleading rho meson decay channels, Eq. (3), (but ignoring IB in the rho meson masses) one gets

$$\Delta\Gamma_\rho = (-0.428 \pm 0.008) \text{ MeV} , \quad (5)$$

(or $\Delta\Gamma_\rho = -0.62(22) \text{ MeV}$, by taking $\Delta m_\rho^{\text{PDG}} = +0.7(8) \text{ MeV}$ [5]).

3 FSR corrections in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$

The final-state photonic corrections to the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$ cross section for center of mass energies \sqrt{s} , $\text{FSR}(s)$, can be identified with the $1 + \delta_0(s)$ corrections to $\rho^0 \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-$, when we allow $m_{\rho^0} \rightarrow \sqrt{s}$. Figure 1 compares our calculation of Ref. [6] obtained in sQED (dotted-line) with the classical Schwinger calculation [9] (red dashed-line) obtained under the same approximation. Although the analytical expressions in both calculations are expressed differently, they clearly coincide numerically, giving support to the above statement.

When we include the structure-dependent electromagnetic vertices in virtual corrections as discussed in the previous section, we get the blue solid line in Figure 1. The largest effects of structure-dependent effects decrease the size of $\delta_0(s)$ corrections by 30% above $\sqrt{s} = 1.2 \text{ GeV}$.

4 Impact on $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi]$

It is customary to express separately the IB effects in $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi]$ arising from different sources in the ratio of form factors $F_V(s)/f_+(s)$ [1, 2, 4]. Using Eq. (1), in Table 1 we compare the results for $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi]$ obtained using the sQED approximation (first two lines) with the results obtained by considering only the structure-dependent effects in FSR and in the radiative corrections to $\rho \rightarrow \pi\pi$ decay (see third line in Table). In this evaluation of IB effects we use the Gounaris-Sakurai shape for the pion form factors $F_V(s), f_+(s)$.

Adding up the new structure-dependent FSR and radiative corrections to $\Delta\Gamma_\rho$ to the corrections from other sources of isospin breaking ($G_{\text{EM}}, S_{\text{EW}}$, phase-space, Δm_ρ , pion mass difference and $\rho - \omega$ mixing) from Ref. [2, 3], we get

$$\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi] = (-11.9 \pm 1.7) \times 10^{-10} , \quad (6)$$

a shift of $+3.1 \times 10^{-10}$ units with respect to the average value reported in [1]. Consequently, after applying the new IB structure-dependent corrections one gets $a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi] = (520.3 \pm$

Source	FSR [$\times 10^{-10}$]	$\Delta\Gamma_\rho(\pi\pi(\gamma))$ [$\times 10^{-10}$] due to $\delta_0 - \delta_+$
Schwinger [9]	+4.67(47) [2]	-5.91(59) [2]
δ_0 (sQED)	+4.64(46) [7]	-5.97(60) [7]
Ref. [7]	+3.77(2)	-1.91(4)

Table 1: Contributions to $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau, 2\pi]$ induced by structure-dependent FSR and $\Delta\Gamma_\rho(\pi\pi(\gamma))$ due to radiative corrections. Results corresponding to sQED approximation are shown in first two lines for comparison.

$1.9 \pm 2.2 \pm 1.7) \times 10^{-10}$ [7]. This result can be compared to the one reported in Ref. [3] ($517.3 \pm 1.9 \pm 2.2 \pm 1.9) \times 10^{-10}$, which differs from our result only in the structure-dependent effects. The last uncertainties in both results corresponds to the IB corrections; it is only slightly reduced due to the explicit calculation of structure-dependent effects.

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References

- [1] R. Aliberti et al., *The anomalous magnetic moment of the muon in the Standard Model: an update*, *Phys. Rept.* **1143** (2025) 1–158, [2505.21476].
- [2] M. Davier, A. Hoecker, G. Lopez Castro, B. Malaescu, X. H. Mo, G. Toledo Sanchez et al., *The Discrepancy Between tau and e^+e^- Spectral Functions Revisited and the Consequences for the Muon Magnetic Anomaly*, *Eur. Phys. J. C* **66** (2010) 127–136, [0906.5443].
- [3] M. Davier, A. Hoecker, A.-M. Lutz, B. Malaescu and Z. Zhang, *Tensions in $e^+e^- \rightarrow \pi^+\pi^-(\gamma)$ measurements: the new landscape of data-driven hadronic vacuum polarization predictions for the muon $g-2$* , *Eur. Phys. J. C* **84** (2024) 721, [2312.02053].
- [4] G. L. Castro, A. Miranda and P. Roig, *Isospin breaking corrections in 2π production in tau decays and e^+e^- annihilation: Consequences for the muon $g-2$ and conserved vector current tests*, *Phys. Rev. D* **111** (2025) 073004, [2411.07696].
- [5] PARTICLE DATA GROUP collaboration, S. Navas et al., *Review of particle physics*, *Phys. Rev. D* **110** (2024) 030001.
- [6] F. V. Flores-Baez, G. L. Castro and G. Toledo Sanchez, *The Width difference of rho vector mesons*, *Phys. Rev. D* **76** (2007) 096010, [0708.3256].
- [7] F. V. Flores-Baez, G. L. Castro and G. Toledo, *Beyond scalar QED radiative corrections: the $\rho^\pm - \rho^0$ width difference, FSR corrections and their impact on $\Delta a_\mu^{\text{HVP,LO}}[\tau]$* , 2510.02723.
- [8] F. Ignatov and R. N. Lee, *Charge asymmetry in $e+e-\rightarrow\pi+\pi-$ process*, *Phys. Lett. B* **833** (2022) 137283, [2204.12235].
- [9] J. S. Schwinger, *PARTICLES, SOURCES, AND FIELDS. VOL. 3*. 1989.